

The Korean War: Joseph Stalin and Mao Zedong, Communist Comrades and Nationalist Rivals

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Abstract

This article examines the Korean War, though rooted in the division between North and South Korea, as profoundly shaped by the power struggles among the Soviet Union, the United States, and China. It focuses on the dynamic interactions and tense rivalries between two of the 20th century's most influential leaders: the Soviet Union's formidable leader Joseph Stalin and China's visionary leader Mao Zedong. The article explores the respective strategic decision-makings by Stalin and Mao regarding the Korean War, setting aside all their other attributes such as the brutal handling of their domestic affairs (Source: Stephen Kotkin, Kotkin 2017, 231-274). Joseph Stalin granted the petition by North Korean leader Kim Il Sung to help reunify the Korean Peninsula by military means. When the defeat of North Korea at the hands of US-led UN forces was imminent, Mao Zedong decided, for its own national security, that China must enter the Korean War.

Overview

The Korean War was initiated by North Korea's Kim Il Sung, endorsed by Soviet Union's Joseph Stalin, and swiftly countered by the US-led UN coalition. The late involvement by China resulted from a difficult decision by Mao Zedong under unfavorable conditions. The back-and-forth diplomatic exchanges and maneuvers between Stalin and Mao played an important role in the outcome of this historical conflict.

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1. Prelude: The Sino-Soviet Friendship and Alliance Treaty

Shortly after the official establishment of the People's Republic of China (PRC) on October 1st, 1949, Chinese Communist Party (CCP) chairman Mao Zedong embarked on his first overseas visit to Moscow on December 16th, 1949. While his main goal was negotiating a friendship/alliance treaty with Joseph Stalin, Mao sought economic aid and tried to persuade Stalin to return several Russian

concessions: they were the Soviet Union's rights to station troops at strategic ports and railroads (Port Arthur, Port Dalian, and Central-Long railway) in China.

These concessions, at the expense of China, were the outcome of the Yalta meeting (Source: [The Yalta Conference](#), Office of the Historian) which Britain's Prime Minister Churchill and the USA's President Roosevelt agreed to, as a reward for Soviet Union for sending its troops to defeat the Japanese forces in the Northeastern Manchuria region of China, after the surrender of Nazi Germany. These concessions were officially codified in a 1945 Sino-Soviet treaty (Source: [Old Sino-Soviet Treaty](#), Wikipedia n.d.) between the Soviet Union and the then governing body of China, the Kuomintang (aka KMT) government. In exchange for these concessions and others (including granting the independence of Outer Mongolia from China, which would be under Russian influence and serve as a strategic buffer zone between Russia and China per Stalin), the Soviet Union agreed not to aid Mao Zedong's communists during future Chinese civil war between KMT and CCP. Nevertheless, even with military aid from the US, the KMT would go on to lose the civil war to the CCP, which had the support from the majority populace of the country. KMT retreated to Taiwan in the aftermath.

The first meeting between Stalin and Mao started on December 16th, 1949. Then negotiations stalled. Mao and his delegates were left in the hotel quarters for weeks, without any activities arranged. Stalin probably did not want to give up all the concessions; he could be concerned that a close alliance with China might trigger a negative US reaction.

The United States sensed this strained relationship between Russia and China; it decided to exploit it. On January 5th, 1950 US President Truman announced a non-interference policy regarding Formosa (aka Taiwan) island and the ongoing China civil war (Source: [Statement on Formosa](#), Truman Library, n.d. “Statement on Formosa”), practically leaving Mao without significant external threats while dealing with a reluctant Stalin. The US hoped this would have driven a wedge between China and the Soviet Union. This new event probably spooked Stalin and compelled the Soviets to move forward with the resuming negotiations on the friendship treaty, culminating in its signing on February 14th, 1950 (Source: [MAO ZEDONG AND STALIN SIGN TREATY IN MOSCOW - 1950](#), Youtube June 4, 2018).

However, the Soviet’s intention to keep the concessions for some time was clear, as evidenced by the minutes of the January 22nd, 1950 meeting (Source: [Record of](#)

[Talks between Stalin and Mao](#), Wilson Center Digital Archive November 20, 2011), specifically regarding the Central-Long railway rights (termed “KChZhD” in meeting minutes). The final friendship treaty stipulated that the Soviet Union would retain the concessions for two more years.

Regarding Soviet monetary aid, Mao wanted it for economic development, while Stalin wanted it to pay for military equipment. From the meeting minutes, Mao felt insufficient money was left for economic development. At the time, the focus of the CCP leadership had shifted toward country-building and post-war economic development, with a large-scale demobilization of its army into the workforce underway. As for remaining military goals, only the Taiwan campaign was left, for which a concentrated strength of half a million troops was stationed on the southeastern coast across the Taiwan Strait, preparing for a sea-crossing battle in the 1950 summer to clean up the KMT remnants. In its northeastern region, close to the border with North Korea, only a few border security forces were stationed responsible for border security. At the time, China was most interested in having a peaceful environment (source: “Secrets of the Korean War”, Shen Zhihua, Hong Kong Tiandi Books, 1995. Shen Zhihua. 1995, 32-64).

Therefore, the discussion of using monetary aid for military purposes in the treaty negotiation would indicate that Stalin likely had anticipated the outbreak of war and was strategically preparing for China's eventual involvement. The war turned out to be the Korean War.

2. Kim Il Sung's Korean War

The two Koreas divided along the 38th parallel line: North Korea and South Korea, were an arrangement between the Soviet Union and the US after the defeat of occupying Japan at the end of WWII (Source: [Korea - Division, History, Britannica](#), n.d.). North Korea was under the control of the Soviet Union, and the South of the US. Later the Soviet Union withdrew its forces from North Korea in 1948, while the United States maintained a token troop of several hundred army personnel in South Korea.

Both Koreas had the desire to conquer the other for a reunified Korea. Kim Il Sung, the North leader, repeatedly asked Stalin for permission and military aid to unify Korea. Stalin was reluctant to approve his request, because of concern that a Korean war would trigger US involvement. On September 24th, 1949 Stalin formally rejected Kim's request to start the Korean War. On October 14th, 1949 Moscow reprimanded the Soviet ambassador to Pyongyang (the capital of North

Korea) for colluding with Kim for taking offensive actions in a small-scale conflict with South Korea (Source: “Historical Truth of the Outbreak of the Korean War”, [朝鮮戰爭爆發的歷史真相](#), Chinese University of Hong Kong, 3).

However, after the US President Truman’s January 5th, 1950 speech regarding Formosa, on January 12th, 1950 the US Secretary of State Dean Acheson gave a more extensive speech on the Far East (Source: [Speech On The Far East](#), Teaching American History). He specifically named Japan and the Philippines under US protection, but left out Korea (“... a new day which has dawned in Asia. It is a day in which the Asian peoples are on their own”). This omission likely caused Stalin to conclude that the US would not interfere in the Korean conflict.

On January 30th, 1950, the Soviet embassy in Pyongyang sent a telegram to Stalin regarding Kim’s openly complaining about the Soviets not allowing him to liberate the South, and his intention to seek help from China instead. This time Stalin replied to the Soviet Pyongyang embassy with a message that “I am ready to help him on this matter.” (Source: “Historical Truth of the Outbreak of the Korean War”, [朝鮮戰爭爆發的歷史真相](#), Chinese University of Hong Kong, 4), a sign of explicitly endorsing North Korean reunification by force. At this time, Mao was still in Moscow working with Stalin on their friendship treaty; yet from the

Chinese surprise reaction a few months later, it was evident that Stalin deliberately withheld the matter of Korean unification from Mao then.

After WWII, the Soviet Union had two strategic contingencies in the Far East: an independent Mongolia as a safety buffer zone between itself and China, and the control of some important Chinese ports and railway: the ice-free ports for year-round access to the Pacific Ocean, and the long central China railway for easy movement of its troops in the Far East. Per the newly negotiated Sino-Soviet treaty, China would take back the port/railway concessions in two years; Stalin needed to take remedial measures. Several ports of Wonsan, Inchon, Busan, and Jeju Island in the central and southern Korean Peninsula were the targets of the Soviet Ministry of Foreign Affairs' attention as early as 1945. To ensure the Soviet Union's strategic interests in the Far East, it became enticing to bring the entire Korean Peninsula into Moscow's sphere of influence, explaining Stalin's change of mind.

With the Sino-Soviet friendship alliance treaty signed on February 14th, 1950, and China formally as its military ally, Stalin probably felt more comfortable with US interference: by then he was in a good position to ask its new ally and aid benefactor to help fight the US.

From Stalin's perspective, if Kim's Korean reunification had worked, the Soviet Union would have expanded its sphere and secured more ice-free Pacific ports. If the US interfered and Kim lost the war, the US could become a more direct threat to China; the Soviet military would have more reason not to leave China. The Soviet Union's presence and influence in the Far East would only increase no matter what.

On March 30th, 1950, just over one month after Mao left Moscow, Kim went to Moscow to meet with Stalin. Stalin told Kim to inform Mao about the upcoming war because they would likely need China's help if the US interfered. On May 13th, 1950, just over one month before the North started the war, Kim went to Beijing to inform Mao. The meeting unsurprisingly did not go well.

In late 1949, before Mao's visit to Moscow, Stalin and Mao exchanged their opinions on the North Korea issue. At the time, they both believed that North Korea should not start offensive military actions. In his mid-1949 telegram to Stalin, Mao informed him that North Koreans had wanted to solve the Korean issue by force, but Chinese leaders had dissuaded them from doing so. Stalin replied that he fully agreed with the Chinese: a Korean war should not be started ("Historical

Truth of the Outbreak of the Korean War”, [朝鮮戰爭爆發的歷史真相](#), Chinese University of Hong Kong, 6).

From Mao’s perspective: the reunification of Korea was a land war and could happen at any time, while the unification of China across the Taiwan Strait, was constrained by many external factors (no navy/air force, weather, seasonal tide). The correct order of operations should be China unification first, and then Korean unification next.

Within this context, Mao was unpleasantly surprised by the secret arrangement between the Soviet Union and North Korea. Since he and Stalin had exchanged a shared understanding of opposing military action in North Korea, the Chinese leader wanted clarification from Moscow. On May 14th, 1950, Mao received the following Stalin telegram, informing a big change in the Soviet Union's attitude toward the Korean issue: “During talks with North Korean comrades, comrade Stalin and his friends proposed that, given the changed international situation, they agreed with the North Koreans on their achieving reunification now. At the same time, comrade Stalin would like to add that this issue must be resolved jointly between the Chinese and North Korean comrades. If the Chinese comrades disagree, the details of the Soviets’s extensive discussions with the North Koreans

can be explained to you by the North Korean comrades”, indicating an uncompromising stance. After Stalin had expressed his support, Mao could no longer refuse Kim Il Sung's request (“Secrets of the Korean War”, Shen Zhihua, Hong Kong Tiandi Books, 78-79).

According to a former senior North Korean munitions officer, before the outbreak of the war, military equipment from the Soviet Union arrived in North Korea by sea, rather than by railroads crossing China. The arrangement was meant to prevent China from learning about the war preparations (“Uncertain Partner: Stalin, Mao, and the Korean War”, Goncharov Lewis Xue Stanford 1993, 23-24). As to the outbreak of the war on June 25th, 1950, Mao learned about it from foreign news afterward. On June 28th, 1950, the third day after the war broke out, Kim Il Sung sent a low-level officer to Beijing to brief the situation. Mao was not amused by this trickery (“When did the Central Committee of CCP decide that volunteers would go abroad to fight?” Li Haiwen, “Party Documentation” Issue 5, 1993, page 85, Li Haiwen 1993, 85).

Kim Il Sung seemed to be smug and full of confidence that he would have a quick victory before the US even had a chance to react. For historical reasons (Korea was subservient to China for a long time), Kim had the motivation to avoid China's

interference in North Korean affairs. Stalin also had concerns about his Chinese ally: it was likely that Mao would oppose this war from the get-go; if the war went ahead, then Mao had every right to stay out of it regardless of the outcome.

Therefore, on the one hand, when Mao was in Moscow working on the friendship treaty (signed on February 14th, 1950), Stalin insulated Mao from his change of heart on the Korean matter, after having given Kim the go-ahead (“willing-to-help” telegram to Kim on January 30th, 1950). On the other hand, Stalin wanted Kim to inform Mao before the war, compelling Mao to give his nod even if grudgingly. If getting the Chinese nod was viewed as asking for a favor, it would be from North Korea, not the Soviet Union. Through such manipulations, Stalin ensured that his strategic effort to control the Korean Peninsula and tactical consideration to use the Chinese army if necessary, were both achieved.

3. External Interventions

Since the US had several hundred soldiers stationed in South Korea before the war, it should not come as a surprise that the US would intervene in the face of North Korean aggression. The question was whether the North Koreans could finish the matter before the US could effectively deploy its reinforcements.

3.1 US-led UN Intervention

On June 25th, 1950, North Korean forces crossed the 38th parallel line and the Korean War started. Two days later, the US sent its 7th Navy fleet to blockade the Taiwan Strait, making it impossible for China to conquer Taiwan. The Korean War went well for Kim initially, as North Korean forces pushed the South Korean and the small U.S. forces back to the Pusan Perimeter in the southeast corner of the Peninsula, but failed to capture the well-defended Pusan harbor. On September 15th, 1950, General Douglas MacArthur led a daring US & South Korean army amphibious landing at Incheon, marking the first turning point for the Korean War. It cut off North Korea's supply lines and caused panic in its troops. On September 25th, 1950, Seoul (the capital of South Korea) was recaptured by the US-led UN forces. North Korean troops were retreating northward in disarray. On October 9th, 1950, US forces crossed the 38th parallel line into North Korea, aiming to push to the Chinese border, completely mop up the remaining North Korean troops, and reunify the Korean Peninsula under South Korean rule.

3.2 China Intervention

Realizing a total defeat of North Korea was imminent, Kim capitulated. On October 1, 1950, Kim swallowed his pride and sent an urgent telegram to Mao, requesting that China directly provide military support. In the letter, Kim said his

enemy was already attacking areas north of the 38th parallel: by then, South Korean forces had already crossed the 38th parallel line.

Historically speaking, the relationship between China and Korea had long been such that Korea acted as a tributary state to China. When Japan invaded Korea in the late 1600s, the Ming Dynasty of China sent an army of 50,000 personnel to defeat the Japanese invaders in Korea. That act was motivated by China's obligation under its tributary system. It was probably under this historical context that Mao would forgive Kim for playing trickery and earnestly consider lending a helping hand to North Korea.

The Chinese Communist Party Politburo held an emergency discussion on the Korean situation: almost no one was interested in the war. Mao expressed his opinion that when a neighbor was in trouble, it would not reflect well on China if it looked on with folded arms; he also pointed out that should the US defeat North Korea, China could face threats from three different geographic directions simultaneously: one from Korea, another from the Taiwan Strait, and a third from Vietnam. However, the Politburo leadership was overwhelmingly against getting involved, citing two major reasons: 1. After many years of war and unrest, as one of the world's poorest countries, China needed to avoid war and rebuild the nation;

2. The US was the most powerful country and had the most advanced military in the world with atomic weapons; China's military, with poor equipment and inadequately trained for modern warfare, was no match for the US as an opponent. On October 2, 1950, Mao sent a telegram to Stalin, stating that the Politburo decided not to send troops. He also said China would carry on troop deployment preparations at the border area just in case.

Zhou Enlai, Premier of China and also the foreign minister, summoned India's ambassador to China on October 2, 1950, requesting India to relay a diplomatic message to the US government through the Indian embassy in Washington, D.C., that if only South Korean troops crossed the 38th parallel line, Korean conflict would remain a civil war. But if the US troops crossed the 38th parallel line, China would take the Korean issue into its own hands (Source: [Transcript of Conversation Between Zhou Enlai and KM Panikkar](#), Wilson Center Digital Archive, April 7, 2021).

The US brushed aside the warning as a bluff. Based on the poor outcomes of all wars between China and its foreign adversaries during the past century from 1840 to 1945, particularly the anti-Japanese invasion effort during WWII as led by the KMT government, the US attitude toward China military strength was well

grounded: even though the communists overwhelmingly defeated the KMT in its most recent civil war from 1945 to 1949, it meant little when judging its military prowess.

The Chinese Politburo continued its debate at the October 5, 1950 meeting. Mao argued that China didn't seek out this war, but was forced upon. The question was no longer whether to send troops, but when to send them. His opinion was that China should send troops before North Korea's capital Pyongyang fell to the advancing US/UN forces. Chinese army general Peng Dehuai (Source: [Peng Dehuai](#), Wikipedia n.d.), whom Mao had chosen as the leader for the Korean situation, attended the meeting; Peng offered his strong support for intervention, even if China could lose it all. It was at this meeting that the Politburo officially decided to intervene. General Peng was charged with assembling a Chinese Voluntary Army (CVA) for the Korean War.

On October 7, 1950, the United Nations passed resolution No. 376, authorizing the US-led UN forces to cross the 38th parallel. The Soviet Union, one of the five permanent security council members with veto power, for unclear reasons, was absent from casting its vote to stop the resolution.

There was speculation that the Soviet Union wanted the US to cross the 38th line and to drag China into the war, playing a war of attrition to weaken the US army using the Chinese Army and North Korean Army, reducing the pressure it faced from the US on the European front.

On October 8, 1950, Mao formally telegraphed Kim that China would send troops to Korea. On October 9, 1950, the US Army 1st Cavalry Division crossed the 38th parallel line and advanced toward Pyongyang.

As early as July 5th, 1950, shortly as the Korean War started, Stalin made a proposal to the Chinese leadership that if China could send 9 divisions of army into the Korean War, the Soviet Union would provide an air force of 124 fighter jets to support the Chinese army (Source: [The War to Oppose U.S. and Aid Korea, Ep. 1: The Inside Story of the Decisions](#), Youtube May 27, 2019, 35m:29s). On October 11, 1950, Premier Zhou was dispatched to Russia to meet with Stalin to coordinate Soviet air support.

However, this time, Stalin told Zhou, that due to logistics reasons, the Soviet air force wouldn't be ready for another two to two and half months. Since the Soviet

Union had airports throughout the Far East, some even in China, the two-month plus preparation time was really not necessary.

What had happened, but what Stalin did not tell Zhou (note: evidence shows even today the Chinese military historians still haven't connected the dots on this matter), was that on October 8, 1950, a US aircraft mistakenly bombed a Soviet airport close to the China/North Korea border (Source: [When the USAF Attacked a Soviet Airbase](#), Military Matters). Worried that the Soviets would seek revenge, the US immediately apologized to the Soviet Union through the UN envoys, stating that the commander of the responsible air force group had been relieved and the two pilots would be disciplined. The US even offered restitution for the damage. However, this incident made the Soviets worry that it was either a threat or a deliberate provocation; any confrontation could lead to a direct war between the Soviet Union and the US. It likely contributed to Stalin's hesitation in providing air support to the Chinese army.

On October 12th, 1950, Mao received a joint telegram from Stalin and Zhou, informing him of the two-month plus unavailability of the Soviet air force. This surprising turn of events prompted the Chinese Politburo to pause, and mull whether to move forward with troop deployment for the second time.

Zhou continued negotiations with Stalin in Russia. He finally issued an ultimatum statement: only if the Soviets sent its air force, would China send its ground force. Since Kim's remaining army could only hang on for days, not months, this condition meant the end of Kim's North Korea.

Stalin resigned and gave in, accepting that the war would be a complete defeat for North Korea, knowing this defeat would reflect very badly on the entire communist bloc that Stalin was leading. Stalin and Zhou agreed to have Kim Il Sung set up a government in exile in Northeast China.

Mao would surprise everyone. On October 13th, 1950, Zhou received a telegram from Mao, informing him that the Politburo had decided once again to send troops. The telegram read that China must participate in the war; the benefits of participation are great, but the harms of non-participation are even greater. Mao also had two concerns which he wanted Zhou to communicate with Stalin. In the meantime, Mao directed General Peng to prepare its troops for departure in four days, on October 17th, 1950.

The two concerns were: 1. Lack of money to immediately pay for any military equipment the Chinese army would need from the Soviet Union, inquiring if they could be treated as a loan and repaid later. 2. Firm commitment of Soviet air force: if the 2-plus month wait time could be ensured, China would bear casualties while waiting.

Stalin was so adamant about avoiding direct conflict with the US, that he would back-pedal further. After a couple of days of deliberation, on October 16th, Stalin responded to Zhou regarding the two concerns: 1. Military aid: the Soviet Union agreed to treat it as a loan with a deep discount, and the payment could be made after the war. 2. Air force: even if the Soviets were to provide an air force after two months, they would remain inside China, along the Yalu River, to protect Chinese air space from intruding US airplanes: there would be no Soviet air force support on the battleground in Korea. Zhou was flabbergasted.

Upon hearing this news, Mao immediately ordered General Peng to hold off on his troop deployment scheduled for the next day. The Chinese Politburo leadership faced the same agonizing dilemma for the third time.

It became clear to Mao that for the Soviets, the outcome of the Korean War was not crucial, only ancillary, to its interests in the Far East. For China, it was a question of having a peaceful border environment for nation building. Due to geological proximity, the US military stationed on the Korea/China border would pose an imminent threat to China's industry base in the northeast and its capital city of Beijing.

Mao believed that even without Soviet air support, his army still had a fighting chance, provided they managed to utilize their hard-earned mature tactical experiences and persist in battling the US army on Korean soil, eventually forcing war resolution at the negotiation table (Source: [The War to Oppose U.S. and Aid Korea, Ep. 1: The Inside Story of the Decisions](#), Youtube May 27, 2019, 42m31s).

On the October 18th, 1950 Politburo meeting, Mao Zedong implored his colleagues that Pyongyang was under attack, and in a few days, the US/UN forces would be at the Yalu River; China must not change its mind, and the time to deploy troops must not be delayed further. The Politburo finally decided on troop set-off for the next day, October 19th, 1950 (Source: [The War to Oppose U.S. and Aid Korea, Ep. 1: The Inside Story of the Decisions](#), Youtube May 27, 2019, 43m37s).

On October 19, 1950, US/UN forces took down Pyongyang, effectively ending the North Korean resistance. On the same day, the Chinese 13th Army Group, led by General Peng, crossed the Yalu River for Korea.

On the night of October 19, Mao could not sleep, till he was informed that the 13th Army Group had entered Korea. According to Mao's assistant for many years, the Korean War was one of his two most difficult decisions; the other one was to break apart with the KMT during the 1946 civil war avoidance negotiations (Source: [Mao Zedong attends 43-day Chongqing Negotiations](#), Youtube July 28, 2021).

The Chinese army conducted its first offensive campaign, from October 25 to November 5, 1950, achieving initial but significant tactical success. They inflicted heavy casualties on the numerically disadvantaged US/UN forces and halted their advance toward the Yalu River, marking yet another turning point in the war. The Chinese army also suffered substantial casualties due to their lack of heavy weaponry and air force. Seeing this success by the Chinese Army, Stalin deployed the Soviet air force in early November 1950, well ahead of the previously stated schedule. As stipulated earlier, the Soviet air force operated primarily along the Yalu River, the border area dubbed "MiG Alley" between China and North Korea, throughout the Korean War. The Soviet pilots flew MiG-15 fighter jets and

engaged in fierce air battles with the US pilots flying F-86 fighter jets. To hide their identities, Soviet airplanes carried Chinese markings; Soviet pilots wore Chinese uniforms and spoke in Chinese on radio communications.

4. Back to the Beginning

At the end of the conflict, with the North-South Korea division line more or less back at the 38th parallel line again (North Korea lost a little bit of territory), the Korean War practically achieved nothing for either Korea. Nevertheless, we can examine the outcomes of the conflicts: who benefited from it, and who suffered its adverse consequences.

4.1 Who Benefitted

1. The United States, by preventing North Korea from crushing South Korea, stopped the spread of Soviet-led communist influence in Northeast Asia and inadvertently caused the Soviet Union to lose all ice-free ports for year-round access to the Pacific Ocean. Its determined interference also sowed the seed for mistrust between China and the Soviet Union, leading to the eventual breakup of their partnership in the 1960s, paving the way to the eventual demise of the Soviet bloc in 1990. (Long-term)

2. Japan, having been stripped of its major industrial capabilities to penalize its involvement in WWII, was awarded contract work by the US military for the Korean War. With all prior restrictions removed, it quickly recovered its economy and achieved extraordinary development for four decades, ultimately becoming the second-largest economy in the world in the 1990s. (Both short-term and long-term)

3. KMT in Taiwan, facing an imminent attack by half a million PLA troops in the summer of 1950, was saved by the US 7th fleet preemptively blocking the Taiwan Strait two days after the Korean War broke out. (Both short-term and long-term)

4. South Korea, saved by the US from a near defeat by a militarily stronger North Korea, aided subsequently with sustained economic assistance from the US, became a major technological and industrial power in East Asia. (Long-term)

5. North Korea, saved by China from a total defeat, benefited from strong Soviet economic aid after the war and was more prosperous than South Korea for quite some time. That prosperity ended when the Soviet Union collapsed in the 1990s. (Medium-term)

6. The Soviet Union, by using the Chinese army, successfully tied down a substantial amount of US military power, particularly its navy and airforce, in Korea and Taiwan Strait, essentially conducting a proxy war of attrition to weaken US military power. (Short-term)

7. China, for its critical role in the Korean War, obtained the leverage to rescind from the Soviets all concessions Stalin extracted out of the KMT, to receive substantive industrial aid from the Soviets for nation-building, and to create a strategic buffer zone out of North Korea. Soviet industrial aid played no small part in converting China from a traditionally agricultural nation into an early-stage industrial nation, laying the ground for its 1980-2010 transformation into the largest industrial country in the world today. (Long-term)

4.2 Who Suffered

1. Both North and South Korea suffered heavy military and civilian casualties and asset losses, without accomplishing reunification for either side. (Short-term)

2. China, due to US's overwhelming military power and air superiority, suffered enormous losses of humans (close to 200k deaths, many times more injuries) plus material resources, and lost the chance of wrapping up its civil war with the Taiwan

campaign planned for the summer of 1950 (although, there was a possibility that the US announcement in January 1950 on non-interference in Chinese civil war was only meant to split China from the Soviet Union and nothing more: the US would not allow Taiwan to fall if China started the Taiwan campaign. The counterargument was that the US did not directly interfere in China's mainland civil war even with troops stationed in China then, and there were no US troops in Taiwan, so US intervention in Taiwan would be highly unlikely as compared to the situation in Korea). After the Korean War (and later the Vietnam War), China entered a long period of hostility with the US and was isolated from the Western-dominated international stage for many decades. (Both short-term and long-term)

3. The Soviet Union lost the respect of China as a reliable senior partner, as Mao felt betrayed by Stalin in the whole setup of this Korean War. This war deepened the mistrust between the two largest partners in the communist bloc that led to the eventual split up of this partnership in the 1960s (Source: [How Tensions Grew Between Mao's China & Khrushchev's Soviet Union](#), Youtube June 18, 2020, 9m39s). (Long-term)

Leadership Comparison

Stalin demonstrated himself to be a great leader for the Soviet Union and an excellent strategic thinker. The war essentially played out just like he had envisioned/planned all along: a strong US intervention with which North Korea couldn't cope, the eventual draw-in of China to turn the tide, all while avoiding the risk of any large-scale direct conflict between the Soviet Union and the US.

Mao proved himself to be a fearless leader and a visionary thinker: he foresaw potential long-term harm to China if North Korea were to be destroyed, overruled the objections of the entire Politburo leadership, took on the enormous risk of sending ill-equipped Chinese troops to confront the formidable US forces, even as its most powerful ally refused to provide air support at the most critical moment for his decision-making.

United against a common adversary – the capitalist United States – the two communist leaders went to great lengths to safeguard their respective national interests. Ultimately, they were both nationalists at heart.

Summary

Upon the insistence of Mao Zedong, the Soviet Union was to return its China concessions, particularly the two Pacific-bound ice-free ports per the Sino-Soviet

peace treaty. For Joseph Stalin, it was a low-risk gamble to let North Korea's Kim Il Sung try to take over the entire Korean peninsula, for regardless of the outcome, Stalin would probably end up enhancing Soviet military presence and influence in Far East Asia. To avoid direct conflict with the US, Stalin declined to provide air support to China as promised. Perceiving the US occupation of North Korea as dangerously encroaching on China, Mao Zedong decided to send troops to Korea, pushing UN forces back to the 38th parallel line and preventing North Korea from total defeat. However, this intervention came at a steep cost, with large numbers of Chinese casualties and resource loss that severely strained the newly established government of China. The war's evolution showcased Joseph Stalin's strategic foresight and tactical planning to advance the Soviet's national interests in East Asia, while carefully minimizing risk. In contrast, Mao Zedong's resolute decision-making demonstrated his determination to protect China's national interests, underscored by his risk-taking and optimism in the face of overwhelming challenges.

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